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THE MAIN DIRECTION OF ENSURING AND STRENGTHENING FOOD SAFETY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: In the article, the food of the national and world economy some issues of ensuring safety are highlighted. Uzbekistan the current state of the agro-industrial complex and its food security its importance in providing has been studied. As well as the population of the country the priority of ensuring the need for food products directions have been determined. Measures and proposals for ensuring food safety are given.

Key words: Food safety, food market, food import, modernization of agriculture.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются продукты питания национального и мирового хозяйства. освещены некоторые вопросы обеспечения безопасности. Узбекистан современное состояние агропромышленного комплекса и его продовольственная безопасность изучено его значение в обеспечении. А также население страны приоритет обеспечения потребности в продуктах питания направления определены. Приведены меры и предложения по обеспечению безопасности пищевых продуктов.

Ключевые слова: Безопасность пищевых продуктов, продовольственный рынок, продукты питания. импорт, модернизация сельского хозяйства

It is known that the food industry is the food of the national economy It is considered a wide range of industries that produce products it contains meat, milk, oil,

fish products, flour, cereals, fruits and vegetables, scanned goods, various drinks, sugar, bread and other food has integrated the enterprises producing its products into its structure. One of the blessings created by nature during the development of human society used. The increase in the number of the world's population in food products led to an increase in demand. Control in food and agricultural production includes the regulation of food production and the protection of the food supply and consumers. In developed countries, quality control measures play a key role in agricultural operations to ensure that food products meet certain safety and quality standards.

These measures include checking for bacterial contamination, measuring fat, protein and other nutrients, and inspecting plants, livestock and production facilities. However, controlling food quality in agricultural value chains poses some challenges. In developed countries, food manufacturing companies implement internal control processes and obtain external control services from impartial and independent competent organizations. Consumers may be concerned about two issues when purchasing food products. The first is whether the food products produced by the enterprise meet the quality standards, and the second is whether the processing adequately responds to these data.

Today, agricultural pest control strategies are primarily concerned with food security. Common pest control methods include synthetic pesticides, biopesticides, chemical pest control, and integrated pest management. When the resistance of some pests to chemical pesticides is combined with the potential health risks to the environment, biopesticides have emerged as an alternative to synthetic pesticides. However, their shelf life and specific effects on target organisms have not been fully determined.

The following are internal factors of food safety is:

used in the production of food products in agriculture size, quality of land and water resources and the possibilities of their effective use; produce food products, including environmentally friendly products; introduction of innovative technologies in the field of production, storage and sale; degree; food produced in the country in

domestic and foreign markets level of competitiveness of products; the state of development of the potential of the national food industry; ratio of import and export of food products; the demand for food products of the broad strata of the population supply at the expense of domestic production in terms of types, volume and quality of products degree; the growth rate of consumer goods prices in accordance with the income of the population; variety and quality are guaranteed, it is popular in domestic and foreign markets sustainability of local seed and seedling supply; breeding of domestic animals and domestic breeds systematic organization of selection and breeding work to increase productivity done; demand and existence of a proposal coordination system; required for the production of agricultural food products stability of supply of material and technical resources and prices of products and material and technical resources used for their production and displayed proportionality of the level of increase in the prices of services.

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